

CBCS

QUALITY STANDARDS FOR ASSAY DEVELOPMENT AND SCREENING AT CBCS

Version 2024.1

This guideline describes routines and quality measures for data generated from assay development and screening at CBCS. The procedures and statistical measures are aligned with the routines of EU OPENSREEN and ensure that CBCS conforms with the general criteria for high throughput screening internationally.

Table of Content

Compound storage at the screening site	3
Robotics and Automation	3
Assay quality criteria.....	3
Reagent quality control	3
Intra-plate quality control	3
Pilot screen	4
Documentation of screening procedure	5
Validating hits	5
Formulas and Definitions	6
Explanation of terms.....	7

Compound storage at the screening site

Assay-ready plates will be stored sealed at -20°C, below 25% of humidity condition. Upon thawing, assay-ready plates are used immediately as a whole batch. Storage time of assay-ready plates is not limited but will always be recorded and kept to a minimum.

Stock plates will be stored sealed at -20°C, below 25% of humidity condition. Stock plates may undergo a maximum of ten freeze-thaw cycles. Stock plate storage time is kept to a minimum, and the duration will always be recorded. The number of freeze-thaw cycles of stock plates and liquid handling, i.e., the number of transfers from the stock plates, are always recorded.

If any precipitation occurs in the stock plates at the beginning/during freezing/thawing, it is documented, but no further action should be taken.

Robotics and Automation

Develop and follow Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for operating instruments.

Perform quality analysis according to instrument manufacturers' advice and perform assay-specific quality control of equipment before starting a screening project.

Assay quality criteria

Reagent quality control

Biochemical reagents

For biochemical assays, reagents (e.g., proteins, enzymes, buffers) shall be stable in the experimental conditions tested for the entire run duration using these reagents. Signal stability should be evaluated as part of the assay development.

Batch or Lot number should be recorded and if possible, the same batch should be used throughout the experiment (FBS etc).

Cell line quality control

Ideally, if not obtained directly from the supplier, the quality and integrity of cell lines used for drug screening should be proven through short tandem repeat (STR) profiling (https://www.atcc.org/en/Products/Cells_and_Microorganisms/Testing_and_Characterization/STR_Profiling_Analysis.aspx; <https://eurofinngenomics.eu/en/genotyping-gene-expression/genotyping-services/microsatellites-str-fla-idaa/>). In addition, mycoplasma testing is also recommended.

Intra-plate quality control

DMSO Tolerance

DMSO-related assay sensitivity should be determined before starting the assay. Minimum DMSO tolerance is defined as the DMSO concentration that does not negatively affect assay readout (i.e. enzyme activity or cell viability) in signal variation from wells without DMSO. The signal should not deviate more than 20% from the signal without DMSO. As a rule, the assay system should tolerate 1% DMSO for biochemical screens and at least 0.1% for cell-based screens.

Z'-factor and robust Z'-factor

The minimum Z' factor cut-off ($Z' > 0.5$) (Zhang JH, 1999) is applied per default for reader-based biochemical and cellular screens. A $0.4 < Z' < 0.5$ can be accepted for cellular assays if the total number of hits can be validated in follow-up assays. This must be demonstrated by screening the pilot library. When Z' cut-off is not applicable, an alternative method to assess whether the response in an assay is significant can be defined.

The use of robust Z'-factor where the standard deviation is replaced by robust standard deviation [median absolute deviation (MAD) $\times 1.483$] and mean by the median in the Z'-factor equation is allowed to remove the influence of outliers (Murray D, 2016).

Coefficient of variation

When the Z'-factor cannot be applied, data variability will be reported instead of using the coefficient of variation (CV%). CV% refers to the sample population of a screening plate. CV% must be lower than 20%.

Minimum Significant Difference

Priority will be given to Z'-factor and CV%. When a sufficient number and range of XC50 values can be measured, Minimum Significant Difference (MSD) will be used as an additional parameter for assessing assay reliability. MSD represents the smallest efficacy difference between two compounds that is statistically significant (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK83783/>). MSD lower than 20 is suggested. If MSD is not applicable, inter-day variation CV may be used instead. At least three replicas in three independent days should be carried out to check inter-day variability.

Plate variation (within one plate), Plate-to-Plate variation, Same-day variation, day-to-day variation

Pilot screen

A pilot screen with a sub-library comprising 1-10 plates is performed once to validate assay performance and robustness. The pilot screen establishes the assay protocol, data evaluation, estimation of hit rate and test for the robustness of the assay against compound-induced measurement artefacts (as frequently caused by cytotoxicity, auto-fluorescence, or aggregation).

Positive and negative controls

When available, the following number of controls will be used:

- 8 controls/ 96-well plate (4+4)
- 32 controls/ 384-well plate (16 + 16)

Negative controls must consist of the reactions with no compound (DMSO only) and be present on each testing plate. Ideally, reference compounds are used for generating the positive control. Only in the absence of known compound standards or if the effect on assay readout is unstable other measures for generating the positive controls are acceptable (e.g. knock-out cell lines for cellular assays or wells without enzyme for biochemical assays).

Hit-rate

The acceptable range for the hit rate will be defined at the beginning of each screening campaign (1-5% is normal). Whenever possible, a counter-screen should be identified, and in case of elevated hit rates, the screening site may insist on establishing a counter-screening protocol.

In the case of very low hit rates, the screening campaign is stopped (assay sensitivity is too low). In the case of high hit rates (assay specificity too low), the compound concentration can be reduced, or the activity threshold for a hit can be changed.

Failure rate

After initial quality control, at most 20% of the measured plates must be remeasured. An initially failed plate (excluding technical failures) can be repeated but to a maximum of 3 repetitions.

Correction of plate patterns and outliers

Spatial pattern correction algorithms (like b-scores) are not recommended. Hardware-based correction for spatial patterns might be acceptable (e.g., the flatfield correction from the Perkin Elmer Envision system). Intra-plate normalisation to reduce plate patterns will be allowed only in particular assays/ readouts, and it should be justified before the screening campaign begins.

Outlier correction will not be allowed for single-dose assays. All data must be recorded and, if necessary, flagged as “inconclusive”.

Regarding control wells, outliers (3σ) can be removed as follows: up to 1 positive OR 1 negative control in the 96-well plate format, up to 2 positive AND 2 negative controls in the 384-well plate format (or, in general, 1/8 of the control wells). However, reasonable activity ranges can be applied for hit definitions (e.g. no activities below negative controls).

Outlier correction is allowed for dose-response assays. Outlier values removed for XC50 calculation should be uploaded together with the accepted data points and be flagged as outliers.

Documentation of screening procedure

- English language will be used for all documentation related to the projects.
- Operational and instrument running logs will be recorded and stored at the screening site.
- Operational logs are written by the person performing the screening, and a copy is stored at the screening site.
- Information on reagents (supplier and batch number) will be recorded and stored at the screening site. The PI is responsible for long-term storage of data.

Validating hits

CBCS recommends the following after a screen.

- 3 concentrations hit confirmation and counter assay, estimating ~150-200 compounds) (CBCS) for a screen of around 40k compounds.
- 7-11 concentration-response curves, estimating 30-60 compounds (CBCS).

Formulas and Definitions

- a. The parameters for Z prime calculation are the standard deviations of the positive (σ_p) and negative (σ_n) and means of the positive (μ_p) and negative (μ_n) controls.

$$\mathbf{Z' factor} = 1 - (3(\sigma_p + \sigma_n))/(|\mu_p - \mu_n|)$$

$$\mathbf{standard deviation: } \sigma = \sqrt{\sum(x - \mu)^2 / N}$$

$$\mathbf{Coefficient of variation: } CV = \sigma / \mu$$

σ = standard deviation, x = each value in the population, μ = mean of the values, N = number of values

- b. **Single dose active compound:** average plus/minus three standard deviations. Special assays might benefit from deviating criteria. Alternative criteria must be defined upfront and approved by the screening site.
- c. **XC50** = half-maximal response concentration (IC50, EC50 or AC50)
- d. **Dose response active compound:** an XC50 value lower than the highest tested dose
- e. **XC50 values will be calculated according to the following definitions:**
- A minimum of 7-11 data points (concentrations) are used for calculating an XC50.
 - A minimum of 2 replicas for each experimental data will be used.
 - Dose-response curve fitting is done using the four-parameter logistic model as

$$\mathbf{y = Bot + (Top - Bot) / (1 + 10^{(\log_{10}(IC_{50}) - \log_{10}(x)) * slope})}$$

Bot: minimal response

Top: maximal response

IC50: concentration of drug at the symmetric inflexion point

slope: the slope of the tangent to the curve when the concentration is IC50 (Hill-coefficient).

x: concentration

y: response

default.

- If the positions of IC50 and x are interchanged in the formula, the sign of the slope is changed.
- For each assay, limitations of parameters are specified.
- An XC50 must be within the tested range - no extrapolation is allowed. XC50s outside the tested range are specified as: > [highest tested dose] (inactive) or "< [lowest tested dose]"
- XC50 error will be reported as error range (95% confidence interval) and fitting quality using R square.
- An XC50 must have a minimum visible activity change (activity difference between the highest and lowest tested dose, determined using the fitted curve) of at least 25% in the case of IC50. In the case of EC50, this value must be defined in the biological context of the assay. 25% is a minimal visible activity change, but other values >25% can be set for specific experiments and reported along with EC50 data.

Explanation of terms

ASSAY(s) shall mean bioassay(s) in which a procedure is carried out containing experiments for determining the biological activity of COMPOUND(s) by measuring one or multiple effect(s) on a biomolecule, an organism, a tissue, a cell line or a biological model compared to control compounds.

PRIMARY ASSAY is the first assay performed in the screening campaign. The primary assay aims to identify primary hits, which are potentially biologically active chemical entities.

SECONDARY ASSAYS are the additional assays following the hit validation stage to confirm the biological activity of chemical entities via a different type of assay or to eliminate certain active compounds based on their mechanism of action, toxicity or activity profile. **SECONDARY ASSAYS** can also include selectivity and specificity assays.

CONFIRMED HITS are compounds initially identified as hits in the primary assay and then retested at the same concentration (ideally in at least duplicates) in the same assay to exclude technical false positives.

COUNTER ASSAY is the assay run to eliminate those hits from the primary and confirmatory assay stages that are not of interest due to their artificial or non-selective activity

ASSAY READY PLATE is the screening plate containing a small aliquot of the compound to be screened, sufficient for a single ASSAY.

VALIDATED HIT is a term for a putative biological activity of a compound, validated by a dose-response curve and usually expressed as an EC50 (for stabilisers and activators) or an IC50 (for inhibitors) value. This is accompanied by a lack of activity in assay-relevant counter screens and independent confirmation of compound purity and identity.

DATA shall mean information output by any sensing device. This present contract defines all information about a compound's physical and chemical properties (for instance, mass spectra trace, molecular weight, etc.), and all physical-chemical or biological information originates from a) bio profiling assessment and b) screening assays.